

Supplementary information to Clinical & Experimental Allergy article:

A new vicilin-like allergen in hazelnut giving rise to a spectrum of IgE binding low molecular weight N-terminal fragments

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Conflict of interest statements: LM, MH, HP, HL, BP and JL are employees of Thermo Fisher Scientific. AV is an employee of Laboratory Corporation of America.

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MATERIALS AND METHODS

Molecular biology

Juvenile hazelnuts were collected near Uppsala (Sweden) and stored at -70°C. Kernels were ground in liquid nitrogen in an RNaseZAP (Ambion) treated mortar and total RNA preparation was carried out using the RNeasy Mini Kit (Qiagen). Poly-A RNA purification was performed using the MagJET mRNA Enrichment Kit (Fermentas).

5' RACE of Cor a 11 mRNA was performed using the SMARTer RACE 5'/3' Kit (Clontech) and the universal forward 5' primer UPM together with with gene-specific reverse primers. Resulting PCR products were cloned into a pRACE vector for DNA sequencing.

cDNA synthesis for cloning purposes was performed using the Maxima First Strand cDNA Synthesis Kit for RT-qPCR (Thermo Fisher Scientific) and random hexamer and oligo(dT)18 primers. PCR amplification was carried out using primers designed to bind outside the coding regions and to carry terminal restriction sites for subsequent cloning. Following cloning in plasmid vectors, multiple clones of each allergen were subject to DNA sequencing. Where required, direct sequencing of primary PCR products was performed to resolve ambiguity.

DNA sequencing was performed on an Applied Biosystems 3130 Genetic analyzer, with reactions prepared using Big Dye Terminator v3.1 Cycle Sequencing Kit (Thermo Fisher Scientific). Templates were prepared from suspended bacterial colonies using TempliPhi (Cytiva) unless primary PCR products were used.

For expression of full-length Cor a 11, including both the vicilin_N and cupin parts, a synthetic gene with codon usage optimized for *Escherichia coli* (ATUM) was cloned into the NdeI and XhoI sites of a pET-23a(+) derived vector, adding an N-terminal hexahistidine tag to enable purification of the protein by immobilized metal ion affinity chromatography (IMAC).

As expression of the entire Cor a 16 precursor sequence was unsuccessful, the vicilin_N and cupin parts were expressed separately. For the N-terminal domain, a subset of five vicilin_N units (#1, #2, #3, #5 and #10), selected to capture the sequence diversity among the 12 peptides, were chosen for expression as a recombinant protein. A synthetic gene (ATUM) encoding these five units in tandem, with codon usage optimized for *Pichia pastoris*, was cloned into the EcoRI and Sall sites of vector pPICZαA, adding a C-terminal hexahistidine tag to enable purification by IMAC. For the cupin part, a

synthetic gene with codon usage optimized for *E. coli* (ATUM) was cloned into the NdeI and XhoI sites of a pET-23a(+) derived vector, adding an N-terminal SUMO tag to increase solubility of the protein¹ and a hexahistidine tag to enable purification by IMAC.

For prokaryotic expression, DNA constructs were transformed into *E. coli* strain BL21-AI. Fermentation was carried out in a 3-litre bioreactor (Belach Bioteknik) and recombinant protein production was induced by addition of arabinose to a final concentration of 0.2% (w/v). Following harvest by centrifugation (10,000 x g, 20 min), the cell pellet was stored at -70°C until use. For expression in yeast, DNA constructs were linearized using SacI and transformed by electroporation into *Pichia pastoris* strain X-33 for chromosomal integration, followed by high-level zeocin selection. Multiple candidates were grown in small scale cultures to screen for expression of the recombinant protein and those showing the highest level were selected. Fermentation was carried out in a 7-litre bioreactor (Belach Bioteknik) with protein production induced by methanol at a concentration of 0.1% (v/v). Cultures were harvested by centrifugation (10,000 x g, 20 min) and the culture medium kept for purification of the recombinant protein.

Protein purification

Low molecular weight proteins were purified from an extract of defatted, freeze-dried hazelnut flour (Allergon, Ängelholm, Sweden), prepared in 100 mM Tris-HCl pH 8.0. After clarification by centrifugation and filtration, the extract was applied to a Q Sepharose FF column equilibrated with Tris-HCl pH 8.0 and eluted with a linear 0-0.5 M NaCl gradient in the same buffer. Selected fractions containing 6-8 kDa bands in SDS-PAGE were pooled and applied to a Source 15 RPC reversed phase chromatography column eluted with a linear gradient of 0-54% acetonitrile in 0.065% TFA buffer. Fractions containing 6-8 kDa bands were identified by SDS-PAGE and analysed by mass spectrometry (MS) and for IgE antibody binding activity. N-terminal sequencing was performed as previously described.²

Mature Cor a 11 was purified from an extract of defatted, freeze-dried hazelnut flour (Allergon, Ängelholm, Sweden), prepared in 50 mM Tris-HCl pH 8.0 containing 10% acetonitrile. After clarification by centrifugation and filtration, the extract was applied to a Q Sepharose FF column equilibrated with 20 mM Tris-HCl pH 8.0 and eluted with a linear 0-0.5 M NaCl gradient in the same buffer. Selected fractions containing 45-50 kDa bands in SDS-PAGE were pooled and applied to an anti-Cor a 11 mAb affinity column. Cor a 11 was eluted in 3.75 M MgCl₂ and applied a Superdex 200 gel filtration column equilibrated and eluted with 20 mM MOPS, 0.15 M NaCl pH 7.6. Fractions containing a 48 kDa band in SDS-PAGE were pooled and finally passed through anti-Cor a 14 and anti-Cor a 9 mAb affinity columns to remove any remaining trace amounts of those allergens. The identity of the protein was confirmed MS.

Protein fragments comprising the cupin domains of Cor a 16 were enriched from a hazelnut extract prepared in 100 mM malonate buffer pH 5.5. After clarification, the extract was applied to an SP Sepharose FF column equilibrated with 20 mM malonate pH 5.5 and eluted with a linear 0-0.5 M NaCl gradient in the same buffer. Selected fractions were applied to a Superdex 200 gel filtration column equilibrated and eluted with 20 mM MOPS, 0.15 M NaCl pH 7.6. Prior to the final step, selected fractions were pooled and passed through a Con A Sepharose column to remove glycosylated proteins such as Cor a 11. The flow-through was applied on a Source 15Q anion exchange column and bound proteins eluted with a linear 0-0.5 M NaCl gradient in 20 mM Tris-HCl pH 8.0. A fraction containing the cupin domains of Cor a 16 was identified by mass spectrometry.

Recombinant Cor a 11 was purified from the soluble fraction of *E. coli* cells after lysis in an Emulsiflex-C5 homogenizer (Avestin). Following addition of imidazole to 5 mM, the filtered centrifugation supernatant was applied to a Ni²⁺-charged Chelating Sepharose FF column and the recombinant protein eluted with a linear 10-375 mM imidazole gradient in 20 mM Tris-HCl, 0.15 M NaCl pH 8.0. Relevant IMAC fractions were pooled and the protein further purified by anion exchange chromatography on a WorkBeads 40Q column (Bio-Works) in 20 mM Tris-HCl pH 8.0 and elution with a linear 0-0.5 M NaCl gradient in the same buffer. Fractions containing rCor a 11 were pooled for a final gel filtration step using a Sephadex 75 column equilibrated and eluted with 20 mM Tris-HCl, 0.15 M NaCl pH 8.5.

The recombinant Cor a 16 vicilin_N domain protein was purified from *Pichia* culture medium after addition of NaCl and imidazole to 0.15 M and 5 mM, respectively, and adjustment to pH 7.5. Following filtration, the conditioned medium was applied to a Ni²⁺-charged Chelating Sepharose FF column and the recombinant protein eluted with a linear 10-250 mM imidazole gradient in 20 mM Tris-HCl, 0.15 M NaCl pH 8.0. Further purification was performed by mixed mode chromatography using a Capto adhere column equilibrated with 20 mM ethanolamine pH 9.5 and elution with a linear 0-1.0 M NaCl gradient in the same buffer.

For purification of the recombinant cupin part of Cor a 16, homogenization and IMAC were performed essentially as described for rCor a 11 above. Further purification was performed by anion exchange chromatography in Tris-HCl pH 8.5 on a WorkBeads 40Q column and elution with a linear 0-0.5 M NaCl gradient in the same buffer.

Except where indicated otherwise, all chromatography media and equipment were obtained from Cytiva (Uppsala, Sweden).

Mass spectrometry

The identity and amino acid sequence of isolated natural hazelnut proteins were established by MS/MS on an Orbitrap Fusion Tribrid instrument (Thermo Fisher Scientific). Prior to the MS analysis, protein samples were reduced by DTT and alkylated with iodoacetamide. The preparation comprising the Cor a 16 cupin domains was enzymatically cleaved with either trypsin or chymotrypsin prior to MS analysis whereas the vicilin_N peptide preparations were subject to top-down MS analysis without enzymatic treatment. ET-HCD, ETD and HCD fragmentation spectra were analyzed with PEAKS Studio software (Bioinformatics Solutions Inc.).

Bioinformatics

Prediction of coding sequences in genome data and exon/intron borders were performed using FGENESH and FGENESH+ (www.softberry.com) and signal peptide prediction using SignalP 5.0 (services.healthtech.dtu.dk/service.php?SignalP-5.0). Molecular mass and isoelectric point were calculated using ExPASy resource Compute pI/MW (www.expasy.org). Alignment of vicilin_N peptides was made using the multiple sequence alignment tool MUSCLE³ (ucgene.net).

Human specimens

Deidentified leftover serum samples of 106 hazelnut sensitized pediatric subjects from the United States were used for the analysis of IgE reactivity to hazelnut allergens in this study. All samples had been submitted to a major laboratory (LabCorp) with a physician's request for analysis of IgE to

hazelnut but without accompanying clinical information. The reported work meets the conditions for exemption from informed consent requirement under the United States Federal Policy for the Protection of Human Subjects (45 CFR part 46). All data were recorded in such a manner that subjects cannot be identified, directly or through identifiers linked to the subjects. Additionally, 11 anonymized plasma samples from an in-house biobank were used, originating from subjects with a doctor's diagnosis of hazelnut allergy and IgE sensitization to Cor a 9 and/or Cor a 14.

Specific IgE antibody measurements

All IgE antibody measurements were performed by ImmunoCAP (Thermo Fisher Scientific), using a Phadia 250 instrument. Experimental ImmunoCAP tests with native and recombinant hazelnut allergens were prepared as described.⁴ Samples with IgE levels greater than the upper limit of the assay's measuring range (100 kU_A/L) were re-analysed after dilution with ImmunoCAP IgE/ECP/Tryptase Sample Diluent (Thermo Fisher Scientific).

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